

WASH Benefits and Serimmune Enterics Immune Repertoire Study

Statistical Analysis Plan

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INTRODUCTION

Background and rationale

Enteric infections are amongst the top causes of morbidity and mortality in children worldwide. There is a critical need for accurate estimation of pathogen-specific disease burden for public health decision-making to 1) identify populations who would benefit most from intervention, 2) prioritize specific interventions to reduce transmission, and 3) assess impact of various intervention strategies (i.e. vaccine, nutrition, water, sanitation and handwashing or WASH). Current burden estimates and intervention studies rely on costly clinical surveillance, which is limited by high proportions of non-medically attended infections, and a lack of capacity for microbial detection in many locations. Serosurveillance, the quantification of antibody responses in serum, is a strategy to provide better estimates of pathogen exposure and risk estimation that overcomes the above limitations. In addition, serologic-based studies also allow for assessment of broad-based impacts in the immune repertoire beyond just the pathogen of interest. Large-scale population-based surveys increasingly collect and test blood to track infectious disease burden and are beginning to be considered for routine monitoring [1,2].

This project will leverage a fully random 12-mer peptide library to perform an unbiased screen across the pathogen proteome to assess the impact that these enteric infections, or interventions to prevent them, can have on an individual's antibody repertoire diversity across pathogens. The WASH Benefits Bangladesh trial provides an ideal setting to assess the value of this immune repertoire assay to measure effects of interventions that plausibly have broad impacts on infection and immune function. In the Bangladesh trial, WASH interventions reduced clinical diarrhea, respiratory infections, enteric protozoan infections and helminth infections [3–6]. At age 14 months, the WASH intervention reduced enteric viral infections but not bacterial infections [7]. The trials' nutritional intervention improved child micronutrient and anemia status, improved growth, and reduced clinical diarrhea [3,8].

Infrequent specimen collection in the trial, at ages ~12 months and ~24 months in the full birth cohort, suggests we have an incomplete picture of the effect of the interventions on pathogen infection. We have shown that ages 6-24 months is the key window for enteric pathogen antibody acquisition in low-resource settings due to high transmission [9]. IgG responses integrate exposure over time so measuring intervention effects on antibody-based measures of infection should provide a more complete picture of impacts on infection. Furthermore, micronutrient supplementation has been shown to improve immune function, so a more complete assessment of the antibody repertoire in the trial could provide new insights into the effect of improved nutrition on immune response vis-a-vis infections and immunizations.

Objectives

Our overall goal is to measure the effects of WASH and nutritional interventions on immune responses to specific pathogens and on broader development of the child immune repertoire in the WASH Benefits Bangladesh trial. For each objective, we will compare children in the

combined WASH+nutrition arm to children in the control arm, who did not receive either the improved WASH or nutrition intervention.

Hypothesis 1: Children ages 6–24 months in the WASH+nutrition arm will have lower immune responses to known antigens of enteric pathogens compared to children in the control arm.

Rationale: Prior analyses in WASH Benefits have demonstrated decreases in active infections in intervention arms compared to the control arm. Since IgG responses integrate exposures over time, we expect this analysis to provide a more complete picture of differences in infection between arms. We anticipate differences in transmission intensity to manifest as differences in quantitative IgG levels (as measured by epitope enrichment scores), seropositivity, and cumulative seroconversion.

Hypothesis 2: Breadth of immune responses may evolve differently over ages 6-24 months among children in the WASH+nutrition arm and children in the control arm.

Rationale: The immune repertoire assay used for this work will allow us to characterize immune responses for all linear epitopes along known immunogenic proteins. If children in the intervention group experience fewer infections during the study, then they could exhibit a more narrow IgG response at the epitope level compared with children in the control group who may have been infected multiple times by the same pathogen. Conversely, if repeated infections lead to a higher specificity of response, then children in the control group may exhibit a narrower breadth (fewer IgG epitope hits) as they age.

Hypothesis 3: IgG responses to vaccine-targeted pathogens may be different among vaccinated children in the WASH+nutrition arm and children in the control arm.

Rationale: Both WASH and nutritional interventions may have an impact on prior pathogenic exposures, microbiome composition, and/or immune function, all of which may play a role in vaccine immunogenicity, especially for oral vaccines.

STUDY METHODS

Study design

WASH Benefits Bangladesh was a cluster-randomized trial designed to generate rigorous evidence about the impacts of sanitation, water quality, handwashing, and nutrition interventions on health and development in early childhood. The trial compared seven arms: control (no intervention), water, sanitation, handwashing, nutrition, combined water+sanitation +handwashing (WASH) and WASH+nutrition. Primary outcomes included diarrheal disease and growth measures. For this pilot study, we will use a sample of children from a substudy that collected venous blood to compare immune responses among children in the control and WASH+nutrition arms at 3, 14, and 28 months (median ages) [10].

Sample size

The sample size for this pilot study was based on cost and logistical considerations. In order to maximize the likelihood of detecting an effect, we will focus on two intervention groups from the trial (control and WASH+nutrition). We will include samples from 60 children in each arm at three follow-up visits (median ages 3, 14 and 28 months), for a total of 360 samples.

Conservatively assuming 50% seroprevalence in the control group at visit 2 (median age 14 months), a sample size of 60 children per group will have at least 80% power to detect an absolute reduction of 25% seroprevalence (from 50% to 25%) with a two-sided alpha of 0.05 using a standard equation for comparison of two proportions. Power for quantitative outcomes including mean IgG expression and number of epitope hits could be higher but due to the novelty of the outcome measurement data are not available to inform power calculations.

STATISTICAL PRINCIPLES

Confidence intervals and p-values

We will report p-values and 95% confidence intervals. All hypothesis tests will be conducted at a significance level of 0.05 and corrected for multiple testing when appropriate. Due to the large number of antigens considered and the exploratory nature of the study, we will use a Benjamini-Hochberg approach to control the false discovery rate (FDR) at a 5% level. Methods for statistical testing and estimation of intervals will differ by analysis and are described in the **Analysis** section.

STUDY POPULATION

A substudy in the WASH Benefits trial enrolled 1512 children in factorial groups control, WASH, nutrition, and WASH+nutrition and measured them at ages 3, 14, and 28 months (median ages) [10]. At each visit, the trial collected venous blood and stored plasma aliquots that will be available for analysis. We propose to test an initial sample set of 60 children with repeated samples at each time point from each of the control and WASH+nutrition arms (60 children x 3 visits x 2 groups = 360 total samples).

Selection into pilot study

We focused on children enrolled in the Control and WASH+N arms of the trial with blood collection at all three visits. To help reduce imbalance between the control and treatment arms in age and measurement dates, we will exclude children with extreme values of age and/or sample collection dates with no overlap between groups during the first visit. We make an exception for Dec 2013 since there were many WSH+N children measured in that month, immediately before many control children were measured in Jan 2014 (one month later).

Inclusion criteria:

- Children enrolled in the Control or WASH+N arms of the trial
- Blood collected at all 3 visits
- Serum sample available based on current sample inventory (as of 02/10/2023)

Exclusion criteria:

- Age <28 days or >200 days at visit 1
- Age <365 days or >548 days (1 to 1.5 years old) at visit 2
- Sample collection from Aug to Nov 2013 at visit 1 (only applies to intervention clusters)

Baseline characteristics

We will report child age at each follow-up visit, child sex, child birth order, and the distribution of calendar dates when samples were collected for each follow-up visit. For each arm, we will also present a number of parental characteristics (e.g. age, years of education), household characteristics (e.g. number of members, number of members <18 years old), and measures of nutrition and WASH status (e.g. household food insecurity, distance to primary water source).

Measurements included in the analysis

The median age for children at visit 1 in the sample is 3 months, meaning that much of the IgG measured at that time could reflect maternal IgG. All measures from visit 1 will contribute to descriptive analyses and observational analyses of these data.

Primary comparisons between the intervention and control groups will focus on measurements among children ages 6 months or older, which we anticipate will come primarily from visits 2 and 3, when children were median ages 14 months (visit 2) and 27 months (visit 3).

ANALYSIS

Immune repertoire assay

Immune repertoire responses will be analyzed using the Serum Epitope Repertoire Analysis (SERA) technology platform (Serimmune, Goleta, CA, USA). A random 12-mer peptide library is displayed on the outer surface of *E. coli* bacteria and mixed with each specimen. 12-mer random peptides were selected based on prior studies reporting that 95% of linear epitopes span fewer than 12 amino acids [11]. Next, antibody-binding peptide library members are separated using magnetic beads, and the genetic sequences of peptide-encoding regions are determined using next generation sequencing (NGS). Genetic sequences are then translated to amino acid sequences for analysis. Computational algorithms have been developed to parse through the vast number of antibody-binding sequences and 1) identify common amino acid patterns (motifs) that differ between diseased and healthy individuals (IMUNE) [12] and 2) identify candidate antigens from arbitrary proteomes (PIWAS) [13]. Our primary inference in this study will focus on PIWAS measurements for immunogenic antigens as summarized below. This

is because motifs identified through IMUNE have not been characterized fully at this time for most enteric pathogens of interest. If motifs become available over the course of this study, we will include them — both as positive control outcomes (e.g., Epstein Barr Virus) and as negative control outcomes (e.g., schistosomiasis, which is not known to be endemic in this study region).

Target pathogens and proteins

Pathogen	Taxa	Proteins	Total Ag
Enteric pathogens			
Norovirus (GI)	Virus	ORF1, CP, VP2	3
Norovirus (GII)	Virus	ORF1, CP, VP1, VP2, POLP	9
Rotavirus	Virus	Primary focus: VP4, VP7 Additional proteins: VP6	3
Adenovirus 40	Virus	Primary focus: CPH, SPIK1, SPIK2, CPP Additional proteins: E1A, E1B, L4, DBP, PVIII, p100K, protease, pVI, POL, IX, PTP, IVa2, L2, pX, E4, NP, E4ORF6, 22K, E3CR1A, E3CR1B, E3RIDA, E3, UXP, E4ORF4, E4ORF3, E4ORF2, pIIIa, E3RIDB, L1	34
Adenovirus 41	Virus	POL, CPP, CPH, L4, E1B, DBP, Ifp, E3CR1B, E1B, IX, IVa2, leader, PTP, L1, L2pMu, UXP, E4orf2, UXP, E4orf2, pVII, L2, pVI, protease, sfp, pIIIa, E3RIDB, E3, E3RIDA, pVIII, E4orf4, E1A, E3CR1A, E4orf3, E4orf6	32
Cryptosporidium	Protozoa	Cp17, Cp23	2
Giardia spp.	Protozoa	VSP3, VSP5	2
Campylobacter spp.	Bacteria	p18, p39	2
Helicobacter pylori (strain ATCC 700392/26695)	Bacteria	flgE, cagA, rplN, rplY, HefD	5

Shigella spp. / enteroinvasive E. coli (EIEC)	Bacteria	Primary focus: IpaA, IpaB, IpaC, IpaD, IpaH3, IpaH32 Additional proteins: fepA, nmpC, pldA, adhesin, cjrA, nlpB, emrK, mdtA, mviN, htrB, sbmA, fhuA	23
Enterotoxigenic E. coli with heat-labile toxin (LT-ETEC)	Bacteria	LTB	1
Enterotoxigenic E. coli with heat-stable toxin (ST-ETEC)	Bacteria	Cs1a, cfab, cs1b, cfac, cfae, cs6a, cs6b, etpa, cota, cotc, cotd, csbD, csbC, csbA, fliC, yghJ, cstA, astC, EatA	19
Vibrio cholerae	Bacteria	CTXB	1
Salmonella typhi (typhoid)	Bacteria	Hyle	1
Vaccine preventable diseases			
Polio	Virus	PolyP, ORF2p	2
Measles	Virus	V, HEMA, FUS, MATRIX, L, PHOSP, NCAP, C	8
Negative control target			
Schistosoma mansoni	Helminth	P40, sm25, k5, rnaseT2, IL4i	5

Outcomes

- Tiling enrichment values and composite scores:** Each bound 12-mer is decomposed into constituent k-mers (typically k=5 or k=6). Enrichment values for each k-mer are calculated by comparing the observed number of unique bound 12-mers containing a particular k-mer to the expected number of k-mer reads in the sample. The expected number of k-mer reads is calculated as:

$$N_s (12 - k + 1) \prod_{i=1}^k p_i$$

where N_s is the number of 12-mer reads in the sample, k is the k-mer length, and p_i is the amino acid proportion for the i th amino acid across all 12-mer reads in the sample (adapted from Haynes, et al. [13]). K-mers can be tiled onto any proteome, and tiling enrichment values are estimated as smoothed values over a window of k-mers. Previous studies have used amino acid-level maximum enrichment value across the protein as a summary measure of an individual's antibody response to a particular

antigen [13]. Here, we will consider the maximum value as in previous studies but will also consider two alternative summaries to characterize a child's breadth of response: a count of the number of epitopes with enrichment values above the 90th percentile (≥ 8 consecutive amino acids above the 90th percentile), and the mean of enrichment values over the entire protein, akin to the outlier sum score proposed by Tibshirani and Hastie for analyses of genomic expression data [13]. For proteins that exhibit clear seroreactive regions based on shared epitope hits across samples, we will limit protein-level summaries to these regions to help focus our inference on areas of maximum signal.

- **Motif enrichment values and composite score:** Motifs are disease-specific amino acid sequences identified using the IMUNE algorithm [12] and are available only for pathogens that currently exist in the Serimmune portfolio (e.g., *Schistosoma* spp., *H. pylori*, *Shigella*). Work related to this study using well-characterized samples from Bangladesh might contribute additional IMUNE motifs for *Salmonella enterica* serovar typhi, *Vibrio cholerae*, and *Shigella*, and additional motifs may be developed through independent work and might be incorporated as additional outcomes (e.g., positive or negative controls) in this analysis. Motifs are based on three to five defined amino acids, and can be interspersed with undefined residues for a total length of up to ten amino acids. Enrichment values are calculated in a similar fashion as described above:

$$N_s (12 - L + 1) \prod_{i=1}^k p_i$$

where L is the total number of residues in the motif and k is the number of defined residues (adapted from Supplemental Information of Pantazes, et al. [12]). Enrichment values are then summed across motifs to create a composite score [14,15]. Availability of this score and corresponding threshold will allow for comparison of motif-based seroprevalence and/or seroconversion between arms.

- **Seroprevalence and seroconversion:** IgG responses will be considered a measure of cumulative exposure to infection over the age range, since we anticipate seroreversion to be rare below age 27 months [9]. Thus, seroprevalence at visits 2 and 3 will be interpreted as a cumulative incidence of seroconversion in the cohort. Protein-level seropositivity will be defined as one or more epitope hits along the protein's amino acid sequence (an epitope is defined as ≥ 8 consecutive amino acids above the 90th percentile enrichment score)[16]. For each pathogen of interest, we will consider a child seropositive if they seroconvert to any protein with > 2 epitope hits measured in the assay.

Statistical methods

Children will be analyzed according to their randomized group (intention to treat).

The primary analysis will combine information from visits 2 and 3 to improve power, accounting for repeated measures within each child. We will exclude measurements among children <6 months old because of the potential contributions of maternal IgG — measurements at visit 1 were collected when children were <6 months old and thus serve to help characterize maternal IgG responses.

Secondary analyses will compare groups at visits 2 and 3 separately to examine age-dependent differences in the intervention effect at median ages 14 months (visit 2) and 27 months (visit 3).

Hypothesis 1: Children ages 6–24 months in the WASH+nutrition arm will have lower immune responses to known antigens of enteric pathogens compared to children in the control arm.

As an initial descriptive analysis, we will plot the tiling enrichment values from each sample for each protein of interest. As described above, the PIWAS score and its corresponding location in the peptide sequence are identified by the highest tiling enrichment value for each sample and protein. For each protein and pathogen, we will compare mean differences between groups in summary enrichment scores (max and mean enrichment values in seroreactive regions) using linear regression with robust standard errors that treat individual study clusters as independent units [17]. As a robustness check, we will estimate permutation P-values for differences between groups using a Mann-Whitney U test, permuting treatment at the cluster level (10,006 replicates).

Similar to known antigens, pathogen motifs in the Serimmune portfolio that were previously characterized and validated in infected and control populations will be considered in the analysis (e.g., *Shigella*). Enrichment values summed over motifs for each pathogen will be compared as described above for the tiling enrichment scores. Previously identified composite score thresholds will be used to categorize likely seropositive and likely seronegative samples for available motifs.

We will compare groups based on seroprevalence and seroconversion by estimating the difference (prevalence difference, risk difference) and ratio (prevalence ratio, risk ratio) between groups. We will estimate differences using a linear-binomial model and ratios using a log-binomial model, with robust standard errors that treat individual study clusters as independent units.

Hypothesis 2: Breadth of immune responses may evolve differently over ages 6-24 months among children in the WASH+nutrition arm and children in the control arm.

To understand the broader immune response and potential differences between arms, we will leverage tiling enrichment data across the entire amino acid sequence for the immunogenic antigens summarized above. Similar to prior antibody repertoire studies measuring epitope hits [18], we will count the number of epitope hits within each protein (defined as ≥ 8 consecutive amino acids above the 90th percentile enrichment score) for each sample. For each protein and pathogen, we will compare the total number of epitope hits as a proxy for breadth of immune

response using a Mann-Whitney U test, permuting treatment at the cluster level (10,006 replicates).

Hypothesis 3: Immune responses to vaccine-targeted pathogens may be different among vaccinated children in the WASH+nutrition arm and children in the control arm.

Immune responses to vaccine-targeted pathogens will act as a positive control – vaccinated children should have antibodies to these pathogens. In Bangladesh, the measles vaccine and the final polio dose are both scheduled to occur around 38 weeks of age; as a result, each follow-up visit represents a distinct window with respect to vaccination (pre-vaccination/maternal antibody at 3 months, shortly after vaccination at 14 months, and >1 year post-vaccination at 27 months). We will investigate breadth of immune responses to vaccine-targeted pathogens as described under Hypothesis 2 above. Depending on the proportion of vaccinated children, we may be able to compare vaccinated and unvaccinated children within the same arm.

Missing data

For this substudy, we will select children with serological measurements at all three time points (see **Study population** section) so do not anticipate missing data.

Statistical software

We will use R statistical software for all analyses (version 4.3 or later). Data and computational notebooks (.R / .Rmd / .html) required to reproduce the analysis will be made publicly available through GitHub and a permanent repository such as the Open Science Framework, Dryad, or Zenodo.

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REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Summary of Changes, Justification, and Timing vis-à-vis key trial events (enrollment completion, interim analyses, unmasking, etc)
1	2021-12-08	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First version
2	2024-01-09	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated protein list based on the final bioinformatics pipeline completed at Serimmune • Note: samples analyzed June 2023, data still blinded/masked to treatment group.
3	2024-08-23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added minimum detectable effect calculations to the sample size section. • For some pathogens, listed primary proteins of interest, segregating them from additional proteins included in the bioinformatics pipelines. For example, narrowing Shigella to Ipa proteins. • Included description of methods to identify seroreactive regions and epitope hits based on initial review of blinded/masked data. • Note: data still blinded/masked to treatment group.
4	2025-03-18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Removed Strongyloides stercoralis from the pathogen list because our bioinformatics pipeline did not include the NIE antigen (primary immunodominant antigen for this pathogen). • Note: Data were unblinded September 1, 2024. Knowledge of results by treatment group had no influence over the decision to remove S. stercoralis.